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Synthesis of four series of quinoline-based heterocycles by reacting 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbonitriles with various types of isocyanides

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Abstract

Four distinct sets of functionalized quinolines were synthesized by reacting 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbonitriles with various types of isocyanides under appropriate conditions. The palladium-catalysed reaction of less hindered aliphatic and aromatic isocyanides with 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbonitriles yielded 2-alkyl(aryl)-1-imino-1H-pyrrolo[3,4-b]quinolin-3(2H)-one derivatives; however, the catalysed reaction of more hindered isocyanides such as tert-butyl isocyanide produced the corresponding 3-cyanoquinoline-2carboxamides. Interestingly, chloroquinoline-3-carbonitriles reacted with ethyl isocyanoacetate in the presence of Cs₂CO₃ to generate imidazo[1,5-a]quinoline derivatives; notably, tosylmethyl isocyanide under the same conditions formed unprecedented 2-tosyl-3-cyanoquinolines.

Keywords: C–C bond formation, isocyanides, palladium, TosMIC, tosylquinolines.